

WHICH FACTORS (QUALITY OF WORK LIFE AND PSYCHOLOGICAL CAPITAL) ARE MORE POWERFUL TO ENHANCE ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOR EMPLOYEE IN LA PATARAI HOSPITAL BARRU

Halijah ¹, Andi Indahwaty AS ², Irwandy ³, Syahrir Andi Pasinringi ⁴,
Fridawati Rivai ⁵ and Nurmala Sari ⁶

¹ Candidate of Master in Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia. Email: hall.halijahapt@gmail.com, ORCHID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2690-8604>

^{2,3,4,5,6} Hospital Administration Study Program, Faculty of Public Health, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia.

Email: ²2idhsidin@unhas.ac.id, ³3irwandy@unhas.ac.id, ⁴4syahrir65@yahoo.com, ⁵5fridarivai@yahoo.com, ⁶6nurmalamrs08@gmail.com

ORCHID ID: ²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9362-0780>, ³<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9224-6240>,

⁴<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5947-2596>, ⁵<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7336-7001>,

⁶<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5518-7720>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11560185

Abstract

This research aims to identify which factors among QWL and Psycap are having the most powerful influence on employee's OCB in La Patarai Hospital, Barru. The type of research used is quantitative research with a cross-sectional design. The population in this study were employees of La Patarai Barru Hospital, totaling 484 people. The sample in this study were employees at La Patarai Barru Hospital using the Slovin formula which amounted to 220 people. The statistics test in this research used is chi-square to see the effect of quality of work life and psychological capital on organizational citizenship behavior and multiple logistic regression to see which variable has the most influence on organizational citizenship behavior. To search the variable with the highest influences use Exp (B) or OR (Odd Ratio) value. Data collection was carried out using a research instrument in the form of which had been tested for validity and reliability which showed that the questionnaire was valid and reliable so that it could be used. The results showed an effect of quality of work life ($p=0.01$) on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees, and there is an effect of psychological capital on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.00$). There is an effect of quality of work life ($p=0.01$) on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees. There is an effect of psychological capital on the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of La Patarai Hospital ($p=0.00$). The variable that most influences the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees is psychological capital, the largest OR (Odds Ratio) = 4.609. Therefore, it is required to nurture the psychological capital including the individual stress level of the workforce is not too high, besides that, recruitment emphasizes the importance of conducting psychological tests so that it adapts to the work environment and workload in the hospital, where the workload and work environment are quite pressurized to be one of the critical consideration factors to be measured through psychological tests, therefore there are several important stages of employee selection, one of which is a psychological test.

Keywords: Quality of Work Life, Psychological Capital, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Hospital, Employee's.

INTRODUCTION

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is a positive behavior of individuals in the organization that is manifested in the form of a willingness to work consciously and voluntarily. The emergence of OCB has a positive impact not only on the individual himself but also contributes to the organization more than what is formally required by the organization. Good and successful organizations have members who go beyond

formal job responsibilities and freely give their time, energy, and thoughts to succeed in their assigned work. Such behavior is not prescribed but contributes to the smooth functioning of the organization [1].

Quality of work life (QWL) is a factor that supports the realization of an employee's organizational citizenship behavior. Quality of work life is one of the variables known to have a close relationship with organizational citizenship behavior. In an organization, quality of work life is very important to be considered as a supporting variable for organizational citizenship behavior. Pradhan, et al 2016 in their research showed that quality of work life affects organizational citizenship behavior. Employees who have a high quality of work life will encourage the emergence of organization citizenship behavior, because they are more likely to speak positively about the organization, are willing to help other individuals, and perform beyond normal expectations [2].

In addition to the quality of work life, one of the variables that influence organizational citizenship behavior is psychological capital. Psychological capital is a positive individual construction that is oriented towards goal success through one's ability to find various paths to success it gives rise to organizational citizenship behavior which can be classified as positive behavior in organizations, so psychological capital may be positively related to organizational citizenship behavior. Psychological capital can lead to desired work behaviors, both those specified in the member's job description and those that are not specified (extra-role) [3].

La Patarai Hospital is a class C hospital owned by the local government and is the only referral center in Barru Regency, South Sulawesi with a full predicate by KARS in 2022. Based on the results of performance measurement for 2021-2023, shows that the community satisfaction index (IKM) has not yet reached the target. The low achievement of the IKM illustrates that the performance of La Patarai Barru Hospital is not optimal. Therefore, it is important to examine the factors that can improve performance at the hospital [4].

Quality of work life plays a key role in improving performance for organizations [5]. By implementing good QWL, employees are healthier, more committed, safer at work produce more goods, and reduce organizational expenses [6]. Psychological capital related to performance can be seen through how much effort individuals show. When an employee tries hard to achieve success, his performance will continue to increase [7]. Purba and Seniati 2004 argue that the benefits of organizational citizenship behavior are that it can increase work productivity [8]. This statement is reinforced by Podsakoff et al 2000, which reveals that organizational citizenship behavior can affect organizational performance [9]. This research aims to identify which factors among QWL and Psycap have the most powerful influence on employees' OCB in La Patarai Hospital, Barru.

METHOD

The type of research used is quantitative research with a cross-sectional design. The research was conducted from February to March 2024. The population in this study were employees of La Patarai Barru Hospital, totaling 484 people. The sample in this study were employees at La Patarai Barru Hospital using the Slovin formula which amounted to 220 people. The analysis used is chi-square to see the effect of quality of work life and psychological capital on organizational citizenship behavior and

multiple linear regression to see which variable has the most influence on organizational citizenship behavior. Data collection was carried out using a research instrument in the form of a questionnaire adopted from Indahwaty Sidin's research which had been tested for validity and reliability which showed that the questionnaire was valid and reliable so that it could be used.

RESULTS

The frequency distribution of the research variables of the quality of work-life variable dimension can be seen in the following table:

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents for Dimensions Quality of Work Life Variable at La Patarai Barru Hospital

No	Variable (n=220)	High	%	Low	%
1	<i>Work Environment</i>	59	26,8	161	73,2
2	<i>Organization Culture And Climate</i>	108	49,1	112	50,9
3	<i>Relation And Co-Operation</i>	60	27,3	160	72,2
4	<i>Training And Development</i>	147	66,8	73	33,2
5	<i>Compensation And Rewards</i>	96	43,6	124	56,4
6	<i>Facilities</i>	148	67,3	72	32,7
7	<i>Job Satisfaction And Job Security</i>	67	30,5	153	69,5
8	<i>Autonomy Of Work</i>	152	69,1	68	30,9
9	<i>Adequacy Of Resources</i>	96	43,6	124	56,4

Source: Primary Data

From Table 1 above, it can be seen that the highest dimension of the quality of work life variable is the autonomy of work dimension, namely 69.1%, and the lowest dimension is the work environment, 73.2%

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents Based on Quality of Work Life at La Patarai Barru Hospital

Variable	High	%	Low	%
<i>Quality Of Work Life</i>	64	29,1	156	70,9
Total	220	100,0	220	100,0

Source: Primary Data

Based on table 2, shows that of the 220 respondents at La Patarai Barru Hospital, 29.1% of respondents with quality of work life were in the high category, and 70.9% of respondents with quality of work life were in the low category.

The frequency distribution of the research variables of the psychological capital variable dimension can be seen in the following table:

Table 2: Frequency Distribution of Respondents for Variable Dimensions Psychological Capital at La Patarai Barru Hospital

No	Variable (n=220)	High	%	Low	%
1	<i>Self-Efficacy</i>	101	55,5	119	44,5
2	<i>Optimism</i>	109	65,5	111	34,5
3	<i>Hope</i>	95	55,5	125	44,5
4	<i>Resiliency</i>	103	70,9	117	29,1

Source: Primary Data

From Table 2 above, it can be seen that the highest dimension of the psychological capital variable is the resilience dimension, which is 70.9%, and the lowest dimension is hope, which is 44.5%.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents Based on Psychological Capital At La Patarai Barru Hospital

Variable	High	%	Low	%
<i>Psychological Capital</i>	109	49,5	111	50,5
Total	220	100,0	220	100,0

Source: Primary Data

Based on table 3, shows that of the 220 respondents at La Patarai Barru Hospital, 49.5% of respondents with psychological capital were in the high category, and 50.5% of respondents with psychological capital were in the low category.

The frequency distribution of the research variable dimensions of organizational citizenship behavior variables can be seen in the following table:

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents Based on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at La Patarai Barru Hospital

Variable	High	%	Low	%
<i>Organizational Citizenship Behaviour</i>	171	77,7	49	22,3
Total	220	100,0	220	100,0

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 shows that of the 220 respondents at La Patarai Barru Hospital, 77.7% of respondents with organizational citizenship behavior were in the high category, and 22.3% of respondents with organizational citizenship behavior were in the low category.

The results of the analysis of the effect of the quality of the work-life dimension of the work environment on organizational citizenship behavior are shown in the following table:

Table 5: Analysis of the Effect of Quality of Work Life on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at La Patarai Barru Hospital

Quality Of Work Life	<i>Organizational Citizenship Behaviour</i>				Total		P-Value
	High		Low		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
High	43	67,2	21	32,8	64	100,0	0,01
Low	128	82,1	28	17,9	156	100,0	
Total	171	77,7	49	22,3	220	100,0	

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 shows that the proportion of respondents who have a high quality of work life with high organizational citizenship behavior is (67.2%) greater than respondents who have a high quality of work life with low organizational citizenship behavior, namely (32.8%). While low quality of work life with high organizational citizenship behavior, namely (82.1%) is greater than the low quality of work life with low organizational citizenship behavior, namely (17.9%). The statistical test results obtained a value of $p = 0.01$, which indicates that there is a significant relationship between quality of work life to organizational citizenship behavior at La Patarai Barru Hospital.

The results of the analysis of the effect of psychological capital on organizational citizenship behavior are shown in the following table:

Table 6: Analysis of the Effect of Psychological Capital on Organizational Citizenship Behavior at La Patarai Barru Hospital

Psychological Capital	Organizational Citizenship Behaviour				Total		P-Value
	High		Low		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
High	98	89,9	11	10,1	109	100,0	0,00
Low	73	65,8	38	34,2	111	100,0	
Total	171	77,7	49	22,3	220	100,0	

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 shows that the proportion of respondents who have high psychological capital with high organizational citizenship behavior is (89.9%) greater than respondents who have high psychological capital with low organizational citizenship behavior, namely (10.1%). While low psychological capital with high organizational citizenship behavior, namely (65.8%) is greater than low psychological capital with low organizational citizenship behavior, (34.2%). The statistical test results obtained a value of $p = 0.00$, which indicates that there is a meaningful relationship between psychological capital to organizational citizenship behavior at La Patarai Barru Hospital.

The results showed the effect between the independent variables together on the dependent variable is as follows:

Table 7: Results of Logistic Regression Analysis of Independent Variables on Organizational Citizenship Behavior in professional personnel at La Patarai Barru Hospital

Variable	B	S.E.	Wald	Df	Exp(B)
<i>Quality of work life</i>	0,791	0,355	4,948	1	0,454
<i>Psychological capital</i>	1,528	0,380	16,204	1	4,609
<i>Constant</i>	0,184	0,699	0,069	1	1,202

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 shows that after multivariate analysis using multiple logistic regression, the logistic regression coefficient value for the variable quality of work life (B_1) = 0.791, and psychological capital (B_2) = 1.528. The p-value of each variable is quality of work life (p-value = 0.01), and psychological capital (p-value = 0.00). By paying attention to the p-value, it can be concluded that the psychological capital variable with the largest Exp (B) or OR (Odds Ratio) value = 4.609, so that the variable is determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behavior.

DISCUSSION

The work environment in the company must be very concerned because it will affect employee performance. According to Mardiana in Sudaryo 2018 work environment is the environment in which employees do their daily work [10]. A conducive work environment will provide a sense of comfort and allow employees to work optimally. The results showed that there was an influence of the work environment dimension on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.03$). This is in line with the results of Yuni's research, Damelina 2023 showing a positive

and significant influence between the work environment on organizational citizenship behavior [11]. The work environment affects organizational commitment [12].

Organizational climate can be interpreted as a form of interaction between people through several experiences they have in the workplace [13]. The results showed that there was an influence of the dimensions of organizational culture and climate on the organizational citizenship behavior of employees of La Patarai Hospital ($p = 0.00$). This is in line with the results of Mega's research in 2021 which shows that organizational culture and climate are positively and significantly correlated with organizational citizenship behavior [14]. The results of Khairuddin's research in 2019 show that there is a positive effect of organizational climate on organizational citizenship behavior [15].

According to Mangkuprawira 2009, one way to maintain and sustain organizational citizenship behavior in employees is by building relationships and cooperation. Relationships and cooperation can be a strong cause for the development of organizational citizenship behavior in an organization. The existence of relation and cooperation will create a culture where self-oriented behavior will be reduced and will turn into task-oriented behavior and the maintenance of the company. This condition motivates a person to take the initiative to do extra work which is a reflection of the attitude of organizational citizenship behavior [16]. The results showed that there was an influence of the dimension of relations and cooperation on organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.01$).

Empowerment is seen to be an important part of ensuring the survival of the organization in a competitive environment [17]. Training is a learning process that involves the acquisition of skills, concepts, rules, or attitudes to improve employee performance [18]. Organizations need skilled knowledgeable employees with the right attitude for the functioning and development of the organization. Therefore, organizations can provide training to improve the skills, and knowledge of their employees. Training and development can bring about major changes in the level of skills, knowledge, and performance of employees [19]. The results showed that there was an influence of training and development dimensions on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.00$). Improving the quality of human resources is one of the keys to winning the increasingly competitive global competition [20].

Compensation and rewards can improve employee performance [21]. Compensation and rewards are very important for employee performance and very important for the organization, so compensation has a positive impact on employee performance [22]. The results showed that there was an influence of the compensation and rewards dimension on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.03$).

Sanusi and Anwar 2005 suggest that work facilities are work completeness that must be owned by the organization. In essence, work facilities consist of facilities and infrastructure. Facilities are everything that is directly related to employees and supports the smooth and successful work process which includes workspace, lighting, and other equipment such as computers, cabinets, tables, chairs, and so on [23]. The results showed that there was an influence of the facilities dimension on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$).

According to Werther et al in Achmad 2018, suggests that job satisfaction is a set of employee feelings about whether or not their job is pleasant [24]. Rivai (Jufrizen & Sitorus, 2021), states that job satisfaction is the real behavior that everyone displays as a work achievement produced by employees by their role in the company [25]. The results showed that there was an effect of job satisfaction and job security dimensions on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$). This is in line with the results of research by Citra, and Justine 2023 which shows job satisfaction has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior [26]. If employees feel job satisfaction, they will carry out their duties optimally, even giving extra effort beyond their basic duties. This can result in organizational citizenship behavior in employees [27].

The results showed that there was an influence of the autonomy of work dimension on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$). Auton Ryan et al 2008 in Hakim and Septarini 2014 stated that autonomy of work can increase job satisfaction because it can create a positive response. An autonomous worker will have the opportunity to achieve goals and intrinsic values, such as self-development, relationships, and community. By receiving these benefits, employees should feel satisfied and happy with their work [28].

A successful organization can perform its human resource management function well. Organizations need employees who are active in the organization, able to do something beyond their formal work (organizational citizenship behavior), and provide performance beyond organizational expectations [29]. The results showed that there was an influence of the adequacy of resources dimension on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.03$).

The results showed that there was an effect of self-efficacy on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$). This is in line with the results of research by Dussault 2006 which states that self-efficacy has a positive influence on organizational citizenship behavior [30]. The high self-efficacy of employees makes them feel more confident, try and to develop strategies for completing challenging tasks [31].

Pessimistic individuals, will not pay attention to positive things and will only focus and assume that what happens is due to their own mistakes. Optimistic individuals become more realistic and flexible. This is because optimism in psychological capital is not only described as a positive and selfish feeling but becomes a strong learning in terms of self-discipline, analyzing past mistakes, and planning to prevent bad things from happening [32]. The results showed that there was an effect of optimism on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p=0.00$).

Hope is the source of organizational commitment [33]. Youssef and Luthans 2007 refer to the fact that positive psychological dimensions such as hope are positively related to organizational commitment [34]. The results showed that there is an effect of hope on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$). This is in line with the results of research by Julianti & Dewayani 2015 which states that the hope sub-variable significantly affects OCB. Individuals who have high expectations will be more diligent and strive to achieve success at work (helping coworkers, having empathy, and personal attention to others) [35]s.

The results showed that there was an effect of resilience on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees ($p = 0.00$). This is in line with

the results of research by Paul, et al 2019 which says that resilience has a significant positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Employee resilience reflects a resilient individual. Resilient individuals are more likely to experience positive emotions even amid difficult situations. Thus, resilience in the workplace will encourage employees to engage in organizational citizenship behavior [36].

Psychological capital is a positive capacity that is included in positive organizational behavior. Psychological capital is the variable determined as the most influential factor simultaneously on organizational citizenship behavior because the higher the psychological capital, the higher the organizational citizenship behavior. Individuals with high psychological capital feel positive affect more often at work. This positive mood is one of the determinants of high and low organizational citizenship behavior. A positive mood will increase the frequency of a person helping others and show other spontaneous prosocial behaviors [37]. Organ 2006 explains that organizational citizenship behavior is a form of behavior that is an individual choice and initiative, not related to the formal reward system of the organization but in aggregate increases organizational effectiveness [38].

The characteristics of psychological capital consist of behavior in positive psychology. The essence of psychological capital is based on the positive psychology paradigm, including psychological conditions based on positive organizational behavior criteria, going beyond human capital and social capital theories, and developing investment and development to restore work improvement and generate competitive advantage [39].

CONCLUSION

There is an influence of quality of work life and psychological capital on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees. The variable that has the most influence on the organizational citizenship behavior of La Patarai Hospital employees is psychological capital.

References

- 1) Hadiwijaya H. Analisis Organization Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Dan Disiplin Kerja Terhadap Prestasi Kerja Karyawan. Semin Nas Teknol Informasi, Bisnis, dan Desain [Internet]. 2017;44–50. Available from: <http://www.news.palcomtech.com/wp-content/plugins/download-monitor/download.php?id=1885>
- 2) Pradan RK. Effect of Work–Life Balance on Organizational Citizenship Behaviour: Role of Organizational Commitment. *Journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0972150916631071*, 2016. 2016;
- 3) Francisca H. Hubungan Antara Psychological Capital Dengan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pada Karyawan PT. PLN (Persero) Distribusi Jawa Tengah Dan Daerah Istimewa Yogyakarta. 2010;0–9.
- 4) LAKIP. RSUD La Patarai Barru. 2023;
- 5) Mousavi, S.H., Monfared S.Y. and HA. Investigating the Relationship Between Life Quality And Productivity In Physical Education Office Employees In Zanjan Province. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences* 15. 3665–3668. 2011;
- 6) Horst D.J., Broday E. E., Bondarick R. S, L. F. PLA. Bondarick R., Serped L. F., Pilatti L. A .2014. Quality of Working Life and Productivity: An Overview of the Conceptual Framework, *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*.Volume 2. Issue 5. June 2014. PP 87-98. 2014;

- 7) Jannah M, Mintarto E, Nurhasan M, Widohardhono R. The Influence of Athlete Students' Psychological Capital on Track and Field Performance. 2018;173:219–21.
- 8) Purba DE, Seniati ANL. Pengaruh Kepribadian Dan Komitmen Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Makara Hum Behav Stud Asia*. 2004;8(3):105.
- 9) Philip M Podsakoff, Scott B MacKenzie, Julie Beth Paine DGB. Organizational citizenship behaviors: a critical review of the theoretical and empirical literature and suggestions for future research, *Journal of Management*, Volume 26, Issue 3, 2000, Pages 513-563, ISSN 0149-2063, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063\(00\)](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0149-2063(00).). 2000;
- 10) Sudaryo, Yoyo., Wibowo Agus., & Sofiati NA. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia*. Yogyakarta: CV.Andi Offset. 2018;
- 11) Yuni D. Pengaruh Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior Yang Dimediasi Oleh Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Karyawan Kantor PT. *Sketsa Cipta Graha, Surabaya Jurnal Ilmiah Wahana Pendidikan*, April 2023, 9(8), 492-497. 2023;
- 12) Jatmiko, E.D., Swasto, B., & Eko G. Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Komitmen Organisasional Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, Volume 21 Nomor 1. 2015;
- 13) Schneider B, Ehrhart MG, MacEy WH. Organizational climate and culture. *Annu Rev Psychol*. 2013;64(March 2016):361–88.
- 14) Mega. Pengaruh Budaya Organisasi Dan Iklim Organisasi Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis Madani* Vol. 3 No. 1. Februari. 2021, 81-95. 2021;
- 15) Khairuddin. Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior Effects of Organizational Climate on Organizational Citizenship Behavior *Journal of Education, Humaniora and Social Sciences (JEHSS)* ISSN 2622-3740 (Online) Vol 2, No. 3, April 2020: 5. 2020;
- 16) Mangkunegara AP. *Perilaku dan Budaya Organisasi, Cetakan Pertama*. PT. Refika Aditama. Bandung. 2009;
- 17) Willda S. Organizational Citizenship Behavior dalam Memoderasi Pengaruh Work Life Policies, Pemberdayaan, dan Training & Development Terhadap Kinerja. *SAINS: Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*. 2020;
- 18) Simamora H. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia, Edisi Ketiga*, Badan Penerbitan Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi YKPN, Yogyakarta. 2006;
- 19) Fath F & W. Pengaruh Motivasi, Insentif, dan Pelatihan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Jurnal Ilmu dan Riset Manajemen*, 5(11), 1-24. 2016;
- 20) Zuhijja L, Azzuhri M. Pengaruh Pelatihan dan Pengembangan SDM Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior dan Kinerja Pegawai Pada Dinas Kebudayaan dan Pariwisata Kabupaten Kediri. *J Ilm Mhs FEB*. 2021;2(2):1–14.
- 21) Saman A. Effect of Compensation on Employee Satisfaction and Employee Performance. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 4 (1) :185-190. 2020;
- 22) Hameed, M., Ramzan, M., Kashif Zubair, H., Ali G, and Arslan M. Impact of Compensation on Employee Performance (Empirical Evidence from Banking Sector of Pakistan). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 5(2) 302-309. 2014;
- 23) Anwar S dan. *Perilaku Organisasi*. Jakarta: Pustaka Jaya. 2005;
- 24) Sudiro. A. The influence of ethical leadership to deviant workplace behavior mediated by ethical climate and organizational commitment. 2018;
- 25) Jufrizen, J., & Sitorus TS. Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Dengan Disiplin Kerja Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Teknologi Edukasi Sosial dan Humaniora*, 1(1), 841856. 2021;

- 26) Citra, Justine (2023) yang menunjukkan job satisfaction berpengaruh positif terhadap organizational citizenship behavior. Pengaruh Job Satisfaction Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Employee Performance Dengan Organizational Commitment Sebagai Variabel Intervening. *Jurnal Ilmiah MEA (Manajemen, Ekonomi, dan Akuntansi)* Vol. 7 No. 3, 2023. 2023;
- 27) Al-Jabari, B., dan Ghazzawi I. Organizational Commitment: A Review of the Conceptual and Empirical Literature and a Research Agenda. *International Leadership Journal*, 11(1), 78–119. 2019;
- 28) Hakim L, Septarini BG. Hubungan Antara Otonomi Kerja Dengan Kebahagiaan Kerja Pada Industri Kreatif (Relation of Work Autonomy with Happiness at Work in Creative Industry). *J Psikol Ind dan Organ*. 2014;03(01):210.
- 29) Priyono & M. Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Sidoarjo: Zifatama Publisher. RZ., Abdul Aziz. 2008;
- 30) Dussault M. Teachers' self-efficacy and organizational citizenship behaviors. *Psychological Reports*, 98(2), 427–432. <https://doi.org/10.2466/PRO.98.2.427-432>. 2006;
- 31) Ingusci, E., Callea, A., Cortese, C. G., Zito, M., Borgogni, L., Cenciotti, R., Colombo, L., Signore F, Ciavolino, E., & Demerouti E. Self-efficacy and work performance: The role of job crafting in middle-age workers. *International Journal of Business and Society*, 20(2), 533–551. 2019;
- 32) Luthans. Organizational behavior. Tenth Edition. International Edition. United States. McGraw-Hill. 2005;
- 33) D. O. The Relationship between the Trust, hope, and Normative and Continuance Commitment of Merger Survivors, *Journal of Management Development*, 25 (9) 870-883. 2006;
- 34) Youssef, C.M & Luthans F. Positive organizational behavior in the Workplace: The impact of hope, optimism, and resilience. *Journal of Management*, 33(5), 774-800. 2007;
- 35) Dewayani J&. Pengaruh psychological capital terhadap komitmen organisasi dan perilaku kewargaorganisasian pada karyawan. *Jurnal Psikologi*, Vol. 8. 2015;
- 36) Paul, H., Bame, U., Ashta, A., Stokes P. Examining an integrative model of resilience, subjective well-being and commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship behaviours. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 27(5), 1274-1297. 2019;
- 37) Jex, M.S., & Britt W. *Organizational Psychology: a scientistpractitioner approach*-2nd ed. New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons, inc. 2008;
- 38) Organ DW. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Good Soldier Syndrome*. Lexington, MA: Lexington Books. 2006;
- 39) Theodora TH, Ratnaningsih IZ. Hubungan Antara Psychological Capital Dengan Organizational Citizenship Behavior Pada Pramuniaga Pt. X Cabang Tangerang. *J EMPATI*. 2020;7(2):682–90.